

CO-DESIGNING COMMUNITY-BASED TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS FOR INCLUSIVE DATA SYSTEMS

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OVERVIEW

This research aims to investigate how solidary actions and ancestral knowledges and values could be embedded in new definitions of social and collaborative technologies and data systems. Likewise, this project seeks to co-create representations of cooperation, technologic ownership, and care in digital spaces.

Grounded in social justice initiatives and alternative economic models, and in collaboration with Tosepan, an indigenous union of cooperatives in Mexico, I will explore how community-led technological efforts may contribute to sharing local knowledges, visualising diverse organisation ideals and imagining new collective data practices.

CONTEXTUALISING THE ENQUIRY

Born in the 70's, the Tosepan Union of Cooperatives was conceived from fights of resistance and defence by the Masewal people from the state of Puebla, Mexico, who decided to create a model that would allow them to subsist and thrive based on their own cosmovision, culture and socio-economic practices, against a capitalist system that was and still is marginalising them and threatening their values, language and identity (Durán, 2018).

Tosepan, which is based in the town of Cuetzalan, operates in 34 municipalities, has 480 local committees and over 48,000 members, 78% of which are Masewal and 64% are women. It is integrated into 9 different coops covering topics across agriculture, micro-finance services, indigenous women empowerment and communications.

I established a relationship with the communications coop, Radio Tosepan Limakxtum (RTL), which over the last 10 years has broadcasted radio shows in Nahuatl, the language of the Masewal, and Spanish, sharing contents to keep the culture, values and the resistance of the territory alive (Benton Zavala, 2018 and Jensen, 2019).

To contextualise the challenges and opportunities that come with the extensive spread of internet access in their territory, its members set up a new project: *Wiki Katat* (translates as 'come, come'), a mobile network based on the same cooperative values and identity. Aligned with this, a share of their profits will be used to generate decentralised contents, as the coop wants *Wiki Katat* users to be able to access, share and contribute to their own platform: *Taewaloni* (translates as 'keeping', 'bag', 'basket').

Currently vaguely conceptualised as intranet, *Taewaloni* aims to become a tool that people in the territory can appropriate and adapt to their particular communities and local cooperatives, while maintaining and spreading the Masewal identity.

IDENTIFYING COMMUNITY VALUES

To commemorate their 40th anniversary, Tosepan published the *Masewal Codex* (taewaloni, 2022) which celebrates and describes the communal and indigenous organisation values and knowledge that have shaped community projects and inspires future strategic plans.

Two ancestral concepts in the *Codex - Tayolchikawalis* and *Tamakepalis* - are vital indigenous practices that RTL aims to integrate into its new technological efforts. These have become core values to inform the qualitative design approach and the participatory nature of the research project:

Tayolchikawalis has been described as 'strengthening the heart' by practicing mutual help, caring and collaboration, encouraging others to participate and be present for each other in times of need.

Tamakepalis translates literally as 'returned hand', and it's the tradition of returning favours through labour, instead of monetary payment. When a Masewal family helps

another through the ‘returned hand’, they know they will receive it too.

These concepts are intrinsically related to cooperation beyond economic imaginaries and they are deeply embedded in the Masewal culture and knowledge. Thus, co-designing with them provides a meaningful framework for exploring how technologies and data could be understood and developed from an indigenous perspective that favours qualitative aspects and cooperation-driven values (Costanza-Chock, S., 2020), in contrast to mainstream technological solutionism.

Visualising intangible (Currie M., 2022 and Hook, J., 2015), non-measurable attributes related to hidden labour, care practices, non-monetary exchanges and informal networks could facilitate appropriation and contribution of data, collected from experiences relevant for people and their context, as mentioned by Feast, L. and Hoshi, K., (2022) and Reitsma, L. et al. (2019).

Developing explorations based on communal needs, curiosity, collective creation and self-ownership, could provide new interpretations of non-extractive data practices (Coudry, N. and Mejias, U.A., 2019). This could help envision scenarios and ideations for *Taewaloni* that follow the strategic lines of the Masewal Codex and that, on a smaller scale, could replicate and translate the organisational and care-driven practices of *Tayolchikawalis* and *Tamakepalis* into the digital domain.

CURRENT WORK AND NEXT STEPS

Through a first on-site fieldwork exploration, with a qualitative protocol that consisted on interviews and a participatory workshop (Andersen, K. and Wakkary, R., 2019), we aim to start generating strategies for the appropriation and adoption of *Wiki Katat* and the early conceptualisation of *Taewaloni*, approached as technological participatory tools that can be co-created and used by the people of the territory.

Initial semi-structured interviews with the wider community that inhabit this area were actively supported, observed and initiated by the RTL members, at times in Nahuatl, and then switching to Spanish for me. The team connected with these participants and facilitated the contact with some of the leaders of the other 8 cooperatives of the union, who participated either in the interviews or in the workshop.

Co-researching both on-site and remotely with RTL, I aim to identify different perceptions, problematisations or expectations of technologies to be addressed by any emerging platforms. Hopefully, this will facilitate ideas around a data system imagined from the perspectives of indigenous values, cooperative processes, mutual care, wellbeing and a safe and informed use of such tools, which should represent diverse knowledges, lived

experiences and feelings. Therefore, it is paramount to approach such concepts from a decolonial lens (Alvarado Garcia, A. et al., 2021 and, Tunstall, E.D., 2023), since the research methods must adapt to the Masewal practices.

INTENDED OUTCOME AND KNOWLEDGE CONTRIBUTION

Taewaloni, as a speculative technology, could be conceptualised in the future as a living data system, a concept that emerges from the living-systems theory, “the dynamics of self-organization, emergence, and resilience taking place within natural and social systems” (Escobar, 2018). Hence, it could become an unfinished (Smyth, M. and Helgason, I., 2017), situated technology “that, rather than being decontextualized and value neutral, is embodied, place based, convivial, and conducive to care” (Escobar, 2018).

Furthermore, this approach has the potential of becoming a data-driven reflection and plural representation of the knowledges, language and cooperative values that the Masewal have practiced and defended for centuries.

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